

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Deliverable 3.2

Report on Consultation on Tenure Track-Like Models

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.150994>

Project Name:	Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE)
Project Number	101094902
Project Duration:	01 January 2023-31 March 2025 (27 Months)
Programme:	Horizon Europe 2021-2027
Call:	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01
Topic:	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-50
Type of Action:	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Granting Authority:	European Research Executive Agency

The SECURE project is financed by European Union through the GRANT AGREEMENT no. 101094902 concluded with the European Research Executive Agency (REA), under the powers delegated by the European Commission.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Information

Title	Report on Consultation on Tenure Track-Like Models
Deliverable:	D3.2
Distribution:	Public
Leader:	CRAC-Vitae, United Kingdom
Author:	Emma Day, Katarina Haluskova and Gareth O'Neill
Date:	11 April 2025
Status:	Final Version V1.0

Document History

Version	Date	Description	Authors/Contributors
V0.1	27/10/2024	Table of contents and methodology of deliverable	Emma Day (Vitae) and Gareth O'Neill (TGB)
V0.2	17/12/2024	First draft of §2 on consultation meetings	Katarina Haluskova (ABIS), Emma Day (Vitae), Silvia Gomez Recio (YERUN), Karolina Karolina Sobczak (ABIS) & Sanja Terlević (YERUN)
V0.3	21/02/2025	First draft of §3 on consultation survey	Emma Day (Vitae) and Gareth O'Neill (TGB)
V0.4	10/03/2025	First full and revised draft version of deliverable	Emma Day (Vitae) and Gareth O'Neill (TGB)
V0.5	11/03/2025	Deliverable reviewed and comments incorporated	Emma Day (Vitae), Eva Hnátková (NCA) & Cornelia van Scherpenberg (VDI)
V1.0	11/03/2025	Deliverable finalised and formally submitted to EC	Emma Day (Vitae)

Contents

Document Information2

Document History.....2

Table of Abbreviations.....4

Acknowledgements6

Executive Summary8

1 Introduction.....8

2. Consultation meetings9

2.1. Consultation Methodology.....9

2.2 Consultation for Researchers.....9

2.3 Consultation with Research Organisations 10

3. Consultation Survey 11

3.1 Survey Methodology..... 11

3.2 Survey Outcomes for TTLMs 13

4 Conclusions 16

References..... 18

Annex 1 - Slides for Consultation for Researchers..... 18

Annex 2 - Slides for Consultation with Institutions..... 22

Annex 3 - Slides for Consultation with Industry Representative.....26

Annex 4 – Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework.....29

Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Name
ABIS	Academy of Business in Society
CET	Central European Time
CRAC-Vitae	Careers Research and Advisory Centre-Vitae
EARTO	European Association of Research and Technology Organisations
EC	European Commission
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, and Occupations
Eurodoc	European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers
ICoRSA	International Consortium of Research Staff Associations
MCAA	Marie Curie Alumni Association
NCA	Not Currently Affiliated
Q	Question
Q&A	Questions and Answers
RCF	Research Career Framework
ResearchComp	European Competence Framework for Researchers
RFO	Research-funding Organisation

Abbreviation	Full Name
ABIS	Academy of Business in Society
CET	Central European Time
CRAC-Vitae	Careers Research and Advisory Centre-Vitae
EARTO	European Association of Research and Technology Organisations
EC	European Commission
RPO	Research-performing Organisation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SECURE	Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment
SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
TGB	Technopolis Group Belgium
TTLM	Tenure Track-like Model
EU	European Union
VDI	VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik
YERUN	Young European Research Universities Network

Table of Figures

Figure 1 - European Framework for Research Careers.....	12
Figure 2 – Responses to survey question “Are TTLMs an ideal way to address precarity?”	16

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all colleagues from our SECURE project partners who helped to prepare and organise and participated in the consultation meetings and survey. We would also like to thank all participants in the open consultation meetings with researchers and representatives of research organisations and industry as well as the public consultation survey. We would further like to thank ERA Policy Agenda Group on Action 4 to 'Promote Attractive Research Careers, Talent Circulation, and Mobility' for their close collaboration with the SECURE project. And we would lastly like to thank Dario Capezzuto, Luísa Henriques, Eva Hnátková, Alis Oancea, and Cornelia van Scherpenberg for their constructive input and feedback during the project and on this deliverable.

Executive Summary

This report is deliverable D3.2 of the SECURE project and presents the outcomes of the public consultation on the SECURE principles for TTLMs, opinions on TTLMs as a means to address precarity and actions on TTLMs as part of the SECURE Research Career Framework. The report is closely linked to deliverable D2.2 of the SECURE project which similarly presents the outcomes of the public consultation on SECURE Research Career Framework. The feedback gathered from the consultation helped to revise and finalise the SECURE RCF and TTLMs.

1 Introduction

This report is Deliverable D3.2 of the SECURE project [1] and presents the outcomes of the **consultation on Tenure Track-like Models (TTLMs)**. The report is linked to deliverable 2.2 of the SECURE project [2] which similarly presents the outcomes of the public consultation on the more detailed Researcher Career Framework as a whole [3]. The aim of the consultation is to gather feedback from the research community on these 2 drafts in order to revise and finalise the RCF and TTLMs. The final versions of the RCF and TTLMs will hereby also take into account the lessons learned from the SECURE trials to implement the RCF [4].

The first draft of the SECURE TTLMs defined nine guiding principles for institutions looking to implement TTLMs. These were stability, transparency, competitive and Inclusive recruitment, fair pay and benefits, recognition through career pathways, professional development, inclusive and healthy working environments, supportive management and responsible evaluation. The RCF included five actions for institutions looking to implement TTLMs.

The **public consultation** consisted of a series of consultation meetings with research stakeholders and a consultation survey on the first draft of the SECURE RCF. The 3 online meetings were targeted at researchers, representatives of research organisations, and representatives of industry, although TTLMs were not considered in the industry workshop as they are not relevant. The online survey was open to all research stakeholders but was targeted especially at researchers. The actions of the RCF were presented in the meetings and survey, alongside the SECURE principles for TTLMS whereby participants were asked to identify priorities and gaps as well as offer suggestions to improve the actions in the RCF and the SECURE TTLMs. The consultation served not only to collect feedback but also to already raise awareness of the RCF and SECURE TTLMs.

This report first describes the main aims, structure, and outcomes of each of the **consultation meetings** for researchers, research organisations, and industry (Section 2). The report then presents the main aims, structure, and outcomes of the **consultation survey** (Section 3). The report closes with a brief **conclusion** of the next steps to revise and finalise the RCF (Section 4).

2. Consultation meetings

2.1. Consultation Methodology

There were 3 consultation meetings **on the Researcher Careers Framework** whereby each meeting was aimed at a specific stakeholder:

- Consultation for Researchers on 16 September 2024
- Consultation for Research Organisations on 17 September 2024
- Consultation for Industry Representatives on 25 September 2024

It is important to note that consultation on the TTLM principles and TTLMs in general formed a part of this consultation, although it was not included in the Consultation for Industry as not relevant for the participating audience.

A registration form was created for each consultation meeting on the Zoom platform (whereby the registration links are now defunct) and was shared widely via the SECURE project social media and via the networks of the SECURE consortium partners. Specific partners also directly engaged their members to encourage participation in the meetings whereby Eurodoc, ICoRSA, and MCAA invited researchers to the researcher meeting, YERUN invited universities to the research organisation meeting, and ABIS invited companies to the industry meeting. Separate privacy policies also needed to be developed for each consultation meeting which conformed with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) due to some participant personal data being collected

A general agenda was developed for the meetings which was planned for a duration of 2 hours from 10.00 to 12.00 CET each day and which first introduced the SECURE RCF and then consisted of 2 break-out sessions on specific discussion topics and a final plenary debrief as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Agenda for SECURE Consultation Meetings

10:00 - 10:00	Welcome and Opening
10:05 - 10:20	Introduction to SECURE Research Career Framework
10:20 - 10:25	Transition to Break-out Sessions
10:25 - 10:55	Break-out Session 1
10:55 - 11:00	Short Break
11:00 - 11:30	Break-out Session 2
11:30 - 11:50	Plenary Debrief
11:50 - 12:00	Q&A and Closing

2.2 Consultation for Researchers

The **consultation for researchers** was held online on the Zoom platform on 16 September 2024 from 10:00 to 12:00 CET. and was organised and hosted by YERUN with Gareth O'Neill (TGB) as the lead facilitator who was supported by break-out room facilitators Katarina Haluskova (ABIS), Silvia Gomez Recio (YERUN), Sanja Terlevic (YERUN), and Emma Day (CRAC-Vitae). A total of 42 out of 45 registered participants consisting of early-career and senior researchers attended the webinar. The main aim of the meeting was to engage researchers in open discussion on the first draft of the RCF and to gather their feedback on the main challenges facing researchers in their research careers and how to improve research careers and specifically how to improve the actions of the RCF.

The meeting for researchers focused on first setting the background and then maximising the discussion with researchers (see Annex 1 for the meeting slides). The **SECURE project** was introduced followed by an explanation of the **Council Recommendation**, relevant **European support measures** for research careers, and the **first draft of the SECURE RCF**. The participants were then divided into **five break-out groups** focused on specific topics which were selected by the participants in advance of the meeting (who could change rooms if they wished). Break-out session #1 focused on **Alternative Careers**, session #2 on **Skills Development**, session #3 on **Working Conditions**, session #4 on **Research Assessment**, and session #5 on **Tenure Track-like Models**.

The **break-out groups** were moderated by a facilitator from the SECURE project who first gave a brief introduction to the specific topic of the break-out session which was structured around key actions proposed in the SECURE RCF related to that topic and which was focused on the relevance for researchers. The moderator then led the discussion and encouraged the researchers to give their views on the topic and suggestions to improve the actions of the RCF related to that topic. The researchers were also asked to provide any additional feedback they might have for the RCF. The moderators took detailed notes of all main points and recommendations to improve the RCF. The key outcomes of the discussion relating to TTLMs are outlined below:

- The consultation revealed mixed experiences with tenure-track systems, with some participants suggesting that tenure-track may not be the only solution to academic precarity. Longer contracts were suggested as a more viable alternative.
- Tenure-track systems must be flexible and adaptable to different career paths, including research and teaching, as well as non-academic routes, and they should not restrict researchers' mobility.
- There was a call for clearer definitions and information on tenure-track positions, more transparent career progression frameworks and improved support for researchers particularly for opportunities in other countries and institutions.
- Concerns were expressed about the number of tenure-track positions that were achievable, leading to false promises that are simply not possible. There is a need to be transparent about the number of people that tenure-track can benefit from as not every researcher can achieve a professorship.

2.3 Consultation with Research Organisations

The **consultation for research organisations** was held online on the Zoom platform on 17 September 2024 from 10:00 to 12:00 CEST and was organised and hosted by YERUN with Gareth O'Neill (TGB) as lead facilitator who was supported by break-out room facilitators Katarina Haluskova (ABIS), Silvia Gomez Recio (YERUN), Sanja Terlević (YERUN), and Emma Day (CRAC-Vitae). A total of 40 out of 51 registered participants consisting of representatives of RPOs, RFOs, and research and technology organisations (RTOs) attended the webinar. The main aim of the meeting was to engage research organisations in open discussion on the first draft of the RCF and to gather their feedback on the main challenges facing research organisations in improving research careers and reducing precarity and specifically how to improve the actions of the RCF.

In parallel to the meeting for researchers, the meeting for research organisations focused on first setting the background and then maximising the discussion with the research organisations (see Annex 2 for the meeting slides). The **SECURE project** was introduced followed by an explanation of the **Council Recommendation**, relevant **European support measures** for research careers, and the **first draft of the SECURE RCF**. The participants were then divided into **5 break-out groups** on specific topics which were chosen by the participants beforehand (who could change rooms if they wished). Break-out session #1 focused on **Alternative Careers**, session #2 on **Skills Development**, session #3 on **Working Conditions**, session #4 on **Research Assessment**, and session #5 on **Tenure Track-like Models**.

The **break-out groups** were moderated by a facilitator from the SECURE project who first gave a brief introduction to the specific topic of the break-out session which was structured around key actions proposed in the SECURE RCF related to that topic and which was focused on the relevance for research organisations. The moderator then led the discussion and encouraged the participants to give their views on the topic and suggestions to improve the actions of the RCF related to that topic. The participants were also asked for any additional feedback they might have for the RCF. The moderators took detailed notes of all main points and recommendations to improve the RCF.

The key outcomes of the discussion relating to TTLMs are outlined below:

- The varying structures of tenure-track models across Europe were discussed. In general they are seen as a potential solution to academic precarity, but a challenge to implement effectively.
- Tenure-track systems should be re-designed allowing for continuous development, maintaining motivation and performance.
- A need for mentoring and clear career frameworks was emphasised, alongside institutional clarity on long-term goals before implementing new schemes.
- A bank of best practices was suggested to help guide institutions in crafting more sustainable academic career models.

3. Consultation Survey

3.1 Survey Methodology

The Survey on the SECURE Research Career Framework 2024 was published openly in the EU Survey Tool and ran from 09 December 2024 until 19 January 2025. The consultation survey was aimed primarily at all stages of researchers as well as at research-related employees and representatives of RPOs and RFOs. The survey was created to gather feedback from the research community specifically on the first draft of the SECURE RCF and TTLMs and more generally on how to improve research careers and reduce the precarity of researchers. The survey consisted of single choice and open response questions and was planned to take around 20-30 minutes to complete. The feedback from survey respondents will contribute to revising and finalising the RCF and TTLMs.

The consultation survey is structured around the first draft of the RCF which in turn is aligned with the 8 pillars of the European Framework for Research Careers in the Council Recommendation as shown in Figure 1. The survey is divided into 12 sections whereby:

- 1 gives a brief introduction to the survey and survey privacy policy
- 2 asks for biographical data on respondents
- 3-10 asks respondents to prioritise and give their views on the 103 actions for each of the 8 pillars
- 11 asks questions focusing on TTLMs
- 12 thanks respondents for their feedback (see Annex 4 for the full survey).

Survey respondents could select 3 types of priorities for the actions: TOP priority for critical actions; HIGH priority for important actions; and LOW priority for less relevant actions.

Figure 1 - European Framework for Research Careers

<p>Pillar 1</p> <p>Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area</p> <p>#1-6</p>	<p>Pillar 2</p> <p>Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers</p> <p>#7-10</p>	<p>Pillar 3</p> <p>Recruitment and Working Conditions</p> <p>#11-15</p>	<p>Pillar 4</p> <p>Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation</p> <p>#16-25</p>
<p>Pillar 5</p> <p>Career Assessment, Development, and Progression</p> <p>#26-30</p>	<p>Pillar 6</p> <p>Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination</p> <p>#31-32</p>	<p>Pillar 7</p> <p>Support Actions for Research Careers</p> <p>#33-39</p>	<p>Pillar 8</p> <p>Monitoring of Research Careers</p> <p>#40-44</p>

2 Survey Outcomes for TTLMs

A total of **323 respondents** filled in the survey who consisted further of **239 researchers** (74%), 44 research managers (14%), 0 research technicians (0%), 12 research support staff (4%), 7 policymakers (2%), and 21 individuals with other professions (6%). This report further focuses on summaries of the responses from the researchers as this group was the primary target of the survey and is considered the most important for feedback to revise the RCF and TTLMs. Relevant responses and comments from the other respondents will also be taken into account where the responses are relevant when revising and finalising the final version of the RCF and TTLMs.

Regarding the **gender** of the 239 researchers: 101 identified as male (42%), 132 identified as female (55%), 4 identified as other (2%), and 2 identified as do not wish to disclose (1%). There was thus a reasonable gender balance across the survey respondents. Regarding the **career stage** of the 239 researchers: 55 were R1 or early-career researchers who conduct research under supervision (23%), 44 were R2 or early-career researchers who have experience but are not yet independent (such as (18%), 95 were R3 or senior researchers who develop their own research (40%), and 45 were R4 or senior researchers who are recognised as leading their research field (19%). More senior researchers therefore responded to the survey than early-career researchers.

Regarding the main **research discipline** of the 239 researchers: 12 were from agricultural sciences (5%), 51 were from engineering and technology (21%), 20 were from humanities (8%), 37 were from medical and health sciences (16%), 43 were from natural sciences (18%), 51 were from social sciences (21%), and 25 did not disclose their research (as they had originally identified as individuals with another profession who did not need to disclose their research discipline but were then reclassified as researchers from their description of their job titles) (11%). All main research disciplines were thus represented in the responses albeit in varying degrees of representation.

Regarding the **type of organisation** for which the 239 researchers work: 184 worked at a university (77%), 40 worked at a research institute (16%), 1 worked at a research association (>1%), 2 worked for the government (1%), 2 worked at a non-profit organisation (1%), 6 worked at a company (3%), and 4 individuals worked at other organisations (2%). The majority of respondents thus work at a university or research institute. Regarding the **country of residence** of the 239 researchers: 51 lived in Romania (21%), 37 lived in Italy (16%), 23 lived in Portugal (10%), 22 lived in Croatia (9%), 10 lived Ireland (4%), 9 lived in Sweden (4%), 17 were from several other countries in the European Union (7%), and 70 were from several countries outside of the European Union (29%).

Respondents to the survey were asked to rate five identified actions relating to TTLMs from Pillar 2 Security of the SECURE RCF that will form part of the research career framework as a top, high or low priority.

The results were as follows:

Action	Priority	Top-High-Low
Engage with national research funders on the need for long term funding for TTLMs	High	120-152-51

Define TTLMs in discussion and close collaboration with researchers at organisations	High	106-162-55
Review regulations and status of TTLMs in national context and locally at organisations	High	95-170-58
Develop an action plan for future implementation of defined TTLMs at organisations	High	106-159-58
Engage with key stakeholders on TTLMs to collect and share best practices on TTLMs	High	78-178-67

All the actions were rated as high priority by respondents so it is difficult to identify what might be of most importance to them. When combining those that are ranked as high and top as they are both indicators of positive preference **Engaging with national funders on the need for long term funding** can be ranked as highest but the difference between all the actions is minimal. They are however, listed in order.

Respondents were then asked a qualitative question on whether they could see any gaps in the actions to address Pillar 5. Most had nothing to add but it was possible to identify a few thematic areas of interest.

- **There is a need for clearer guidance and support on TTLMS to gain understanding and help implementation. There is a concern that this may be disproportionately affecting historically marginalised groups eg. Women and contributing to academic precarity.**
- **There is a need to address the challenges of implementation at national level and have comparability on a European level, with acknowledgement that is extremely difficult to achieve.**
- **There is not one clear solution and there is a need for a variety of acknowledged TTLMs, based on an understanding that not all researchers want to move to a standard academic job with teaching responsibility, however, would still like the opportunity to gain a permanent position.**
- **Whilst undoubtedly providing a solution TTLMs are not the only way to address precarity and there remains a need for a range of pathways with TTLMs being a part of the overall research eco-system.**

Respondents to the survey were then asked to rate the nine Secure principles for TTLMS as a top, high or low priority.

The results were as follows:

SECURE Principle	Priority	Top-High-Low
Stability	Top	226-85-12
Transparency	Top	200-109-14

Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment	Top	151-143-29
Fair Pay and Benefits	Top	232-80-11
Recognition through Career Pathways	Top	171-125-27
Professional Development	Top	185-121-17
Healthy and Inclusive Working Environments	Top	188-111-24
Supportive Management	Top	164-130-29
Responsible Evaluation	Top	180-120-23

Respondents ranked each of the principles as being of top priority which reflects our consortium position when establishing this set of principles. However, some are more clearly endorsed as top than others with the highest being Fair Pay and Benefits (232) and the lowest being Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment (151).

They were then asked an open question as to whether they could see any gaps in the principles. No one that was surveyed identified a significant gap.

Respondents were also asked if they thought TTLMs are the ideal way to reduce the precarity of research careers with a significant percentage agreeing that they are that they are (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – Responses to survey question “Are TTLMs an ideal way to address precarity?”

In a supplementary question asking them to explain their answer, the main themes were:

- Respondents were complementary about the SECURE principles finding them self-

- explanatory with no need for further elaboration.**
- **Many did see TTLMs as an ideal way to address precarity believing that they may be a way to bring about stability and break cycles in which researchers are only able to plan two years at a time. They are seen as being a significant step in the right direction.**
 - **Others were less sure and were keen to highlight the challenges of implementation, with a feeling that for a model to be effective it must be comprehensive and flexible enough to accommodate current diversity and adjust to future changes without too much disruption.**
 - **A significant group of respondents did not consider TTLMs to be ideal, particularly noting that no way is ideal as the issues is deeper and broader than that.**
 - **Challenges of funding were of concern with respondents highlighting that TTLMs can only be implemented when properly funded. There is a need for endorsement from the funders.**
 - **Challenges of national context and law are essential and must be considered.**
 - **There is a need to have clearly defined progression career pathways for researchers to permanent employment or an open contract to provide researchers with security and reduce anxiety.**
 - **There remains a tension between what researchers expect and what is possible, with researchers expecting permanent employment.**
 - **There remain deep concerns about how to address precarity.**
 - **There are also real concerns about pressure on researchers, particularly around mental health and wellbeing.**
 - **There remain concerns about how to tackle key issues, particularly inconsistent funding and lack of jobs.**

4 Conclusions

The consultation and survey phase of this project has endorsed the SECURE principles for TTLMs as being relevant and of value to institutions looking to implement tenure track-like models. Feedback on the principles was extremely positive with the more critical comments questioning what is possible and thereby addressing the underlying challenges of the current academic system. Data from the survey might be used to reconsider the order of presentation of the principles and provide a revised way of presenting them.

There is a need to consider many different pathways and options within TTLMs and more work should be done in collecting examples throughout Europe in order to gain more understanding of the various approaches at institution and national level. The SECURE case studies will therefore be revised to better demonstrate national context and show how the principles work at national, institution and schematic level. Two further additional case studies will be added. This will provide practical realistic examples and contribute to a body of knowledge around approaches to TTLMs.

The survey demonstrated that TTLMs are a popular tool in addressing the precarity of research careers, however, it is important that they are not the only solution for this complex and wide spread issue. Longer contracts could perhaps be considered as a viable alternative that is easier to

implement and addresses the very specific challenges that short term contracts offer. Concerns were expressed about the number of tenure-track positions that are available to researchers and the challenges of promising what is simply not sustainable.

Both the consultation and the survey provided endorsement that TTLMs should consider and map to the Secure TTLM principles, particularly around career and professional development and ensuring there is flexibility in pathways particularly through a variety of entry levels and routes inside and outside of academia. They also appreciated case studies and examples and there is a need for ongoing collection of examples to demonstrate this. This may help with creating more sustainable career pathways for researchers.

Ultimately, precarity of researchers remains an ongoing challenge but TTLMs that are flexible, encourage a positive research culture and provide support for researchers are an excellent way of addressing this when considered in the framework of realistic financial, national and institutional context.

References

[1] Webpage of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project on CORDIS hosted by the European Commission. Link:

[<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094902>]. Accessed 17 April 2024.

[2] O'Neill Gareth (Technopolis Group) & Haluskova Katarina (ABIS).

Report on Consultation on SECURE Research Career Framework

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15099416

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SECURE Research Career Framework

Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14917415

[4] Moya-Falcón, Corina, Priscila Velázquez-Ortuño, Sophie Bouccara, Emma Day, Alina Irimia, Matthieu Lafon, Hélder Lopes, Nataša Jakominić Marot, Panagiotis Moiras, Gareth O'Neill, Isabel Rocha, Alexandra Roman, Ioana Trif, Ana Margarida Venda & Saša Zelenika (2025) Report on Trials to Implement SECURE Research Career Framework. Deliverable D4.2 of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project.

Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/15099450>. Accessed 30 March 2025

Annex 1 - Slides for Consultation for Researchers

The image shows two presentation slides side-by-side. The left slide is the title slide for a consultation. It features the SECURE logo (Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment) and the text 'SECURE Consultation for Researchers'. The presenter is Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group), and the event is on 16 September 2024 Online. A QR code is visible in the center, and the slide is funded by the European Union. The right slide is the agenda, titled 'Agenda', listing the following items: 10:05: Introduction to RCF; 10:20: Transfer to Break-outs; 10:25: Break-out Session 1 [5 Topics]; 10:55: Short Break; 11:00: Break-out Session 2 [5 Topics]; 11:30: Plenary Debrief [5 Debriefs]; 11:50: Question and Answers; 12:00: Closing. The slide is numbered 02 and is also funded by the European Union.

<p>Towards a Council Recommendation on Research Careers</p> <p>14 February 2023 → 13 July 2023 → 18 December 2023</p> <p>Technical Document for ERAC → European Commission Proposal → Council Recommendation</p> <p>04</p>									
<p>Links to Other Key European Initiatives</p> <p>European Charter for Researchers + European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp) + European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations Classification (ESCO)</p> <p>06</p>									
Pillar 1 Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area #1-6	Pillar 2 Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers #7-10	Pillar 3 Recruitment and Working Conditions #11-15	Pillar 4 Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation #16-25						
Pillar 5 Career Assessment, Development, and Progression #26-30	Pillar 6 Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination #31-32	Pillar 7 Support Actions for Research Careers #33-35	Pillar 8 Monitoring of Research Careers #36-44						
<p>Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1</p> <p>Recommendation 1</p> <p>'Researchers' means professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new scientific knowledge based on original concepts or hypotheses. They conduct research and improve or develop concepts, theories, models, infrastructures, techniques, instrumentation, software or operational methods. Researchers may be involved fully or partially in different types of activities - such as basic or applied research, experimental development, operating research equipment in any sector of the economy or society and disseminating and valorising research results. They may also be partially involved in, among others, project management, teaching, mentoring, supporting evidence-informed policy making, open science practices, knowledge and technological transfer activities, and science communication. Researchers identify options for new research and development activities, and plan for and manage them by using high-level skills and knowledge developed through formal education and training or from experience.</p> <p>08</p>									

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<p>List of Potential Implementation Actions for RPOs/RFOs</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Topic</th> <th>Which actions could implement this recommendation of RPOs and RFOs?</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Researchers</td> <td>Adopt the EFRC definition of "researcher" in organisational regulations and policies</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Intersectoral Mobility</td> <td>Encourage more diverse job definitions and rights and obligations of "researcher"</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Intersectoral Mobility</td> <td>Raise awareness on the wide diversity of research careers in and outside academia</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. Intersectoral Mobility</td> <td>Encourage trainees and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5. Intersectoral Mobility</td> <td>Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6. 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Break-out Session 5: Tenure Track

Tenure Track-like Models

- Review regulations and status of TTLMs in national context and locally at organisations
- Define TTLMs in discussion and close collaboration with researchers at organisations
- Develop an action plan for future implementation of defined TTLMs at organisations

Engage with key stakeholders on TTLMs to collect and share best practices on TTLMs

Engage with national research-funding bodies on need for long-term funding for TTLMs

Tenure Track-like Model Principles

- 1 Stability
- 2 Transparency
- 3 Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment
- 4 Fair Pay and Benefits
- 5 Recognition through Career Pathways
- 6 Professional Development
- 7 Inclusive and Healthy Working Environments
- 8 Supportive Management
- 9 Responsible Evaluation

Thank you!

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Annex 2 - Slides for Consultation for Research Organisations

SECURE Consultation for Research Organisations

Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group)
17 September 2024 Online

Agenda

- 10:05: Introduction to RCF
- 10:20: Transfer to Break-outs
- 10:25: Break-out Session 1 [5 Topics]
- 10:55: Short Break
- 11:00: Break-out Session 2 [5 Topics]
- 11:30: Plenary Debrief [5 Debriefs]
- 11:50: Question and Answers
- 12:00: Closing

SECURE Project

SECURE
Grant agreement ID: 101094902

DOI: 10.33027/1094902

EC signature date: 7 November 2022

Start date: 1 January 2023 | End date: 31 March 2025

Funded under: Reforming and enhancing the European RRI System

Total cost: € 1 319 423,13

EU contribution: € 1 288 376,00

The SECURE project will develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity

Towards a Council Recommendation on Research Careers

14 February 2023
Technical Document for ERAC

→

13 July 2023
European Commission Proposal

→

18 December 2023
Council Recommendation

22

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Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

<p>European Framework for Research Careers (EFFRC)</p> <p>06</p>	
<p>SECURE Research Career Framework</p> <p>Interpretation of EFFRC for RPOs/RFOs based on 6 questions per recommendation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs? 2. Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation? 3. How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation? 4. How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers? 5. Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs? 6. Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs? <p>First Draft of SECURE Research Career Framework</p> <p>07</p>	<p>Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1</p> <p>Recommendation 1</p> <p><i>'Researchers' means professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new scientific knowledge based on original concepts or hypotheses. They conduct research and improve or develop concepts, theories, models, infrastructures, techniques, instrumentation, software or operational methods. Researchers may be involved fully or partially in different types of activities - such as basic or applied research, experimental development, operating research equipment in any sector of the economy or society and disseminating and valorising research results. They may also be partially involved in, among others, project management, teaching, mentoring, supporting evidence-informed policy making, open science practices, knowledge and technological transfer activities, and science communication. Researchers identify options for new research and development activities, and plan for and manage them by using high-level skills and knowledge developed through formal education and training or from experience.</i></p> <p>08</p>
<p>Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How could this recommendation be relevant and useful for RPOs and RFOs? <p>Different organisations may adopt a different definition of 'researcher' depending on their own internal or even national regulations and policies. Differing definitions of 'researcher' can limit interoperability and comparability across organisations, sectors, and countries. The semantic meaning of 'researcher' can also differ across languages and translations. This recommendation provides a common definition which can be used across languages, organisations, sectors, and countries. Organisations could adopt this definition of 'researcher' or at least clearly communicate on their own definition of 'researcher'. Researchers could also be made explicitly aware of all of the expected activities as well as formal rights and obligations associated with their role of researcher at their organisation</p> <p>09</p>	<p>Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which principles of the Charter could be relevant for this recommendation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pillar 1 > Principle 6 > The Researcher - Pillar 4 > Principle 1 > Valuing Diverse Research Careers <p>10</p>

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could ResearchComp and ESCO be relevant for this recommendation?

- The adoption and promotion of ResearchComp at an organisation could be accompanied by a clear definition of 'researcher' so that it is clear for whom ResearchComp is applicable
- Organisations could align the classification/tagging of researcher job/grant advertisements with relevant ESCO classifications for occupations, skills/competences, and qualification

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Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- How could this recommendation reduce the precarity of research careers?

The definition of 'researcher' proposed in this recommendation and its adoption or refinement at an organisation could help the organisation define the scope of precarity. Any organisation aiming to reduce precarity in research careers needs to define who is at risk and who is the target of efforts to reduce precarity. Including a clear definition of 'researcher' along with the associated rights and obligations of the role of the researcher in grant/job advertisements could help researchers manage their expectations in their careers

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Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
- Communicate more clearly on the definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'

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Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?

- Definition of 'researcher' may already be defined in local or national regulations
- Semantic meaning of 'researcher' can differ across languages and translations
- Changing definition of 'researcher' in regulations and policies is a complex process
- Researchers may be resistant to changes regarding the definition of 'researcher'

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List of Potential Implementation Actions for RPOs/RFOs

#	A	B	C
7	1	1	1
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24	1	1	1
25	1	1	1

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Break-out Sessions

1
Alternative
Careers

Katarina
Halušková

2
Skills
Development

Sanja
Terlevič

3
Working
Conditions

Silvia
Gomez Recio

4
Research
Assessment

Gareth
O'Neill

5
Tenure
Track

Emma
Day

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<p>Break-out Session 1: Alternative Careers</p> <p><i>Intersectoral Mobility</i> <i>Alternative Careers</i></p> <p>Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility</p> <p>Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector</p> <p>Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers</p> <p>Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility</p> <p>Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility</p> <p>17</p>	<p>Break-out Session 2: Skills Development</p> <p><i>ResearchComp</i></p> <p>Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences for researchers</p> <p>Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers</p> <p>Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies</p> <p>Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences</p> <p>Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp</p> <p>18</p>
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Annex 3 - Slides for Consultation for Industry Representatives

<p>SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment</p> <p>Agenda</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10:05: Introduction to RCF 10:20: Transfer to Break-outs 10:25: Break-out Session 1 [3 Topics] 10:55: Short Break 11:00: Break-out Session 2 [3 Topics] 11:30: Plenary Debrief [3 DebrieFs] 11:50: Question and Answers 12:00: Closing <p>secureproject.eu 02</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>									
<p>Towards a Council Recommendation on Research Careers</p> <p>SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment</p> <p>14 February 2023: Technical Document for ERAC</p> <p>13 July 2023: European Commission Proposal</p> <p>18 December 2023: Council Recommendation</p> <p>secureproject.eu 04</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>									
<p>Links to Other Key European Initiatives</p> <p>SECURE Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment</p> <p>European Charter for Researchers</p> <p>European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp)</p> <p>European Skills, Competencies, Qualifications, and Occupations Classification (ESCO)</p> <p>secureproject.eu 06</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>									
Pillar 1 Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area #1-6	Pillar 2 Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers #7-10	Pillar 3 Recruitment and Working Conditions #11-15	Pillar 4 Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation #16-25						
Pillar 5 Career Assessment, Development, and Progression #26-30	Pillar 6 Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination #31-32	Pillar 7 Support Actions for Research Careers #33-39	Pillar 8 Monitoring of Research Careers #40-46						

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Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which actions could implement this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
 - Adopt the EFRC definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies
 - Communicate more clearly on the definition and rights and obligations of 'researcher'

13

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Example of Our Approach for Recommendation 1

- Which challenges could hinder this recommendation at RPOs and RFOs?
 - Definition of 'researcher' may already be defined in local or national regulations
 - Semantic meaning of 'researcher' can differ across languages and translations
 - Changing definition of 'researcher' in regulations and policies is a complex process
 - Researchers may be resistant to changes regarding the definition of 'researcher'

14

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

List of Potential Implementation Actions for RPOs/RFOs

#	A	B	C
1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1
3	1	1	1
4	1	1	1
5	1	1	1
6	1	1	1
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21	1	1	1
22	1	1	1
23	1	1	1
24	1	1	1
25	1	1	1

15

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Sessions

1
Alternative
Careers

Katarina
Halušková

2
Skills
Development

Sanja
Terlević

3
Working
Conditions

Emma
Day

16

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 1: Alternative Careers

Intersectoral Mobility	Alternative Careers
Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	Raise awareness on non-linear and hybrid research career paths among researchers
Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector	Integrate non-linear and hybrid research career paths into regulations and policies
Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers	Offer career development support for non-linear and hybrid research career paths
Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility	Collect and share best practices on non-linear and hybrid research career paths
Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	

17

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

Break-out Session 2: Skills Development

ResearchComp
Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences for researchers
Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers
Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies
Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transversal skills/competences
Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp

18

Review and internally discuss providing commensurate remuneration for researchers	Review and internally discuss providing more permanent contracts to researchers										
Review and improve support for flexible working conditions and work-life balance	Define a maximum threshold for number of fixed-term contracts and monitoring plan										
Review and improve support for inclusivity, equal opportunities, and gender equality	Review and internally discuss researcher access to relevant social protection benefits										
Review and improve support for academic freedom and protection against interference	Collect and share best practices on improving the working conditions for researchers										
Review and improve support to researchers with the fulfilment of administrative duties											

Annex 4 - Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework

<h3 style="text-align: center;">Survey on SECURE Research Career Framework 2024</h3> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; background-color: #fff9c4; padding: 5px; margin: 10px 0;">Fields marked with * are mandatory.</div> <p>Welcome!</p> <hr/> <p>Welcome to this public survey on research careers and the Research Career Framework from the SECURE project!</p> <p>The survey is aimed at all stages of researchers as well as research-performing and research-funding organisations.</p> <p>The aim of the survey is to improve the Research Career Framework and reduce the precarity of research careers.</p> <p>The Research Career Framework offers actions for organisations to improve and support the careers of researchers.</p> <p>The Research Career Framework is structured around the 8 pillars of the European Framework for Research Careers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pillar 1: Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area • Pillar 2: Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers • Pillar 3: Recruitment and Working Conditions • Pillar 4: Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation • Pillar 5: Career Assessment, Development, and Progression • Pillar 6: Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination • Pillar 7: Support Actions for Research Careers • Pillar 8: Monitoring of Research Careers. <p>This survey is also structured around the pillars and asks respondents to prioritise and give their views on the actions.</p> <p>Select TOP priority for critical actions, HIGH priority for important actions, and LOW priority for less relevant actions.</p> <p>We will use your responses to improve the Research Career Framework and will not share your personal data publicly.</p> <p>The survey consists of single choice and open response questions and will take around 20-30 minutes to complete.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">1</p>	<p>Please respond with your own personal opinion to the questions and not from the perspective of your organisation.</p> <p>See for more information on the draft Research Career Framework by SECURE: https://zenodo.org/records/10776714.</p> <p>See for more information on the draft Tenure Track-like Models from SECURE: https://zenodo.org/records/11496657.</p> <p>• I have read and accept the terms and conditions of the consultation survey privacy policy: https://secureproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/secure_wp23_consultation_survey_privacy_v1.pdf.</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Yes</p> <p>Bio</p> <hr/> <p>(1) What is your name? 100 character(s) maximum</p> <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/> <p>• (2) What is your gender?</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Male <input type="radio"/> Female <input type="radio"/> Other <input type="radio"/> Do not wish to disclose</p> <p>• (3) What is your nationality?</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Austria <input type="radio"/> Belgium <input type="radio"/> Bulgaria <input type="radio"/> Croatia <input type="radio"/> Cyprus <input type="radio"/> Czechia <input type="radio"/> Denmark <input type="radio"/> Estonia <input type="radio"/> Finland <input type="radio"/> France <input type="radio"/> Germany <input type="radio"/> Greece <input type="radio"/> Hungary <input type="radio"/> Ireland <input type="radio"/> Italy <input type="radio"/> Latvia <input type="radio"/> Lithuania</p> <p style="text-align: right;">2</p>
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Luxembourg<input type="radio"/> Malta<input type="radio"/> Netherlands<input type="radio"/> Poland<input type="radio"/> Portugal<input type="radio"/> Romania<input type="radio"/> Slovak Republic<input type="radio"/> Slovenia<input type="radio"/> Spain<input type="radio"/> Sweden<input type="radio"/> Other <p>*Please specify 100 character(s) maximum</p> <input type="text"/>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Luxembourg<input type="radio"/> Malta<input type="radio"/> Netherlands<input type="radio"/> Poland<input type="radio"/> Portugal<input type="radio"/> Romania<input type="radio"/> Slovak Republic<input type="radio"/> Slovenia<input type="radio"/> Spain<input type="radio"/> Sweden<input type="radio"/> Other <p>*Please specify 100 character(s) maximum</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>(4) What is your country of residence?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Austria<input type="radio"/> Belgium<input type="radio"/> Bulgaria<input type="radio"/> Croatia<input type="radio"/> Cyprus<input type="radio"/> Czechia<input type="radio"/> Denmark<input type="radio"/> Estonia<input type="radio"/> Finland<input type="radio"/> France<input type="radio"/> Germany<input type="radio"/> Greece<input type="radio"/> Hungary<input type="radio"/> Ireland<input type="radio"/> Italy<input type="radio"/> Latvia<input type="radio"/> Lithuania<input type="radio"/> Luxembourg<input type="radio"/> Malta<input type="radio"/> Netherlands<input type="radio"/> Poland<input type="radio"/> Portugal<input type="radio"/> Romania<input type="radio"/> Slovak Republic<input type="radio"/> Slovenia<input type="radio"/> Spain<input type="radio"/> Sweden<input type="radio"/> Other	<p>(4) What is your country of residence?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Austria<input type="radio"/> Belgium<input type="radio"/> Bulgaria<input type="radio"/> Croatia<input type="radio"/> Cyprus<input type="radio"/> Czechia<input type="radio"/> Denmark<input type="radio"/> Estonia<input type="radio"/> Finland<input type="radio"/> France<input type="radio"/> Germany<input type="radio"/> Greece<input type="radio"/> Hungary<input type="radio"/> Ireland<input type="radio"/> Italy<input type="radio"/> Latvia<input type="radio"/> Lithuania<input type="radio"/> Luxembourg<input type="radio"/> Malta<input type="radio"/> Netherlands<input type="radio"/> Poland<input type="radio"/> Portugal<input type="radio"/> Romania<input type="radio"/> Slovak Republic<input type="radio"/> Slovenia<input type="radio"/> Spain<input type="radio"/> Sweden<input type="radio"/> Other
3	3

*** Please specify**
100 character(s) maximum

(8) **What is the name of your organisation?**
100 character(s) maximum

(9) **Have you heard of the following European initiatives?**

	Yes	No
• European Framework for Research Careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• R1-R4 Researcher Profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• European Classification of Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations (ESCO)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• RESAVER Pension Fund	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• EURAXESS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• ERA Talent Platform	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• European Charter for Researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Research and Innovation Careers Observatory (ReICO)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Pillar 1

Pillar 1 focuses on Researchers, Research Managers, and Research Technicians in the European Research Area.

This includes actions on researchers, intersectoral mobility, research managers and technicians, and R1-R4 profiles.

Intersectoral mobility refers to the movement and collaboration of researchers across the different societal sectors.

The [R1-R4 profiles](#) identify 4 sequential stages in the careers of researchers from early-career to senior researchers.

The R1-R2 profiles are relevant for early-career researchers and the R3-R4 profiles are relevant for senior researchers.

(10) **How would you prioritise the following actions on the definition of a 'researcher'?**

5

	Top	High	Low
• Adopt a common definition of 'researcher' in organisational regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Communicate more clearly on definition and rights and obligations of a 'researcher'	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(11) **How would you prioritise the following actions on intersectoral mobility?**

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the wide diversity of research careers in and outside academia	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Encourage, train, and support researchers for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Promote value of researchers and their skills/competences to non-academic sector	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Organise research career events and employer matchmaking events for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify structural and administrative barriers to intersectoral collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on support for intersectoral collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(12) **How would you prioritise the following actions on research managers?**

	Top	High	Low
• Define a clear profile for research manager positions with their roles and responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research manager as a research career	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Train researchers in research management and support transition to research manager	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research managers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(13) **How would you prioritise the following actions on research technicians?**

	Top	High	Low
• Define a clear profile for research technician positions with their roles and responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Raise awareness on diverse career paths and research technician as a research career	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6

• Train researchers in technical support and support transition to research technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Support ongoing training, development, and professionalisation of research technicians	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(14) How would you prioritise the following actions on the R1-R4 profiles?

	Top	High	Low
• Adopt the R1-R4 profiles or map existing organisational profiles onto the R1-R4 profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Refer to the R1-R4 profiles in job/grant advertisements and relevant communications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify scope of precarity and propose measures to reduce precarity for R1-R4 profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Treat doctoral candidates as professionals with related working conditions and benefits	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Raise awareness of and support adoption of R1-R4 profiles in the non-academic sector	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(15) How would you prioritise the following actions on the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles?

	Top	High	Low
• Adopt the grouping of R1-R2 and R3-R4 profiles in organisational regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Tailor support measures for career development to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Tailor support measures to address precarity to R1-R2 and R3-R4 profile groups	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(16) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 1?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 2

Pillar 2 focuses on Recognition, Interoperability, and Comparability of Researchers' Careers.

This includes actions on career recognition/interoperability, career pathways, ESCO classification, and human resources.

ESCO is the multilingual classification of European skills, competences, occupations, and qualifications (for researchers).

(17) How would you prioritise the following actions on career recognition/interoperability?

	Top	High	Low
• Track the long-term career paths of researchers at and beyond home organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on recognition and support of diverse research careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders on recognition and support of diverse research careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders on interoperability and comparability of research careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(18) How would you prioritise the following actions on career pathways?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on non-linear and hybrid research career paths among researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate non-linear and hybrid research career paths into regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Offer career development support for non-linear and hybrid research career paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on non-linear and hybrid research career paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(19) How would you prioritise the following actions on the ESCO classification?

	Top	High	Low
• Integrate (updates of) the ESCO classification into research job/grant advertisements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate (updates of) ESCO classification into local/national accreditation frameworks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify changing and emerging skills/competences, occupations, and qualifications	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide recommendations for future revisions of classifications in the ESCO classification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(20) How would you prioritise the following actions on human resources?

	Top	High	Low
• Conduct a review of research career structures and career paths within organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Involve human resources officers and research staff in organisational R1-R4 mapping	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Develop clear documentation, guidelines, and communications on the R1-R4 mapping	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with other human resources offices to share best practices on the R1-R4 profiles <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> 	
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(21) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 2?
1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 3

Pillar 3 focuses on Recruitment and Working Conditions.

This includes actions on recruitment/selection, working conditions, rights/obligations, and pensions /RESAVER.

[RESAVER](#) is a European pension fund which allows researchers to retain pension benefits across jobs and countries.

(22) How would you prioritise the following actions on recruitment/selection?

	Top	High	Low
• Make general recruitment and selection procedures for vacant positions publicly available	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide individual feedback to candidates on results of a specific recruitment and selection	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Inform recruiters and selectors on the value of alternative career paths and career breaks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(23) How would you prioritise the following actions on working conditions?

	Top	High	Low
• Review and internally discuss providing commensurate remuneration for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support for flexible working conditions and work-life balance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support for inclusivity, equal opportunities, and gender equality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support for academic freedom and protection against interference	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and improve support to researchers with the fulfilment of administrative duties	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and internally discuss providing more permanent contracts to researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Define a maximum limit for the number of fixed-term contracts with a monitoring plan	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review and internally discuss researcher access to relevant social protection benefits <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> • Collect and share best practices on improving the working conditions of researchers <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> 	
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(24) How would you prioritise the following actions on rights/obligations?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness regularly on social protection rights and obligations to all researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide individual personalised counselling on social protection rights and obligations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collaborate with external specialists in the field of social protection rights and obligations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(25) How would you prioritise the following actions on pensions/RESAVER?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness about long-term pension planning and RESAVER among researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Take part in RESAVER Pension Fund and join the consortium of member organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(26) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 3?
1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 4

Pillar 4 focuses on Researchers Skilled for Intersectoral and Interdisciplinary Careers and for Entrepreneurship and Innovation.

This includes actions on doctoral training, ResearchComp, entrepreneurship, and interdisciplinary mobility.

[ResearchComp](#) is a framework for researchers to assess and develop relevant research and transferable skills for their careers.

Interdisciplinary mobility refers to the movement and collaboration of researchers across different /integrated research domains.

The [Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training](#) are 7 principles for organisations to improve their doctoral training programmes.

The [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) is for self-regulation of research integrity across

10

disciplines and sectors.

Open Science refers to the opening up of activities and results of the research life cycle (such as open access to publications).

Transferable skills are skills which can be utilised or transferred across different (research) occupations, sectors, and careers.

Entrepreneurship refers to the creation of a new company based on an original idea and assuming the related risks and rewards.

(27) How would you prioritise the following actions on doctoral training?

	Top	High	Low
• Align doctoral training programmes with Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Align doctoral training programmes with European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate policies and practices for Open Science into doctoral training programmes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(28) How would you prioritise the following actions on ResearchComp?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on ResearchComp and transferable skills/competences for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate ResearchComp into training and career development support for researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Integrate ResearchComp into researcher profiles and relevant regulations and policies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on ResearchComp and transferable skills /competences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide recommendations for future revisions of skills/competences in ResearchComp	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(29) How would you prioritise the following actions on entrepreneurship?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on entrepreneurship taking an inclusive and gender equal approach	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Encourage, train, and support researchers for entrepreneurship, start-ups, and spin-offs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Create support offices, hubs, and centres for entrepreneurship and technology transfer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11

(30) How would you prioritise the following actions on interdisciplinary mobility?

	Top	High	Low
• Encourage, train, and support researchers for interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on supporting interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(31) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 4?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 5

Pillar 5 focuses on Career Assessment, Development, and Progression.

This includes actions on mobility recognition, research assessment, career support, and tenure track-like models.

In a tenure track-like model (TTLM) a fixed-term contract leads to a permanent position subject to positive evaluation.

[Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) consists of organisations aiming to reform research assessment.

(32) How would you prioritise the following actions on mobility recognition?

	Top	High	Low
• Recognise international collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise intersectoral collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise interdisciplinary collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise virtual collaboration and mobility activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(33) How would you prioritise the following actions on research assessment?

	Top	High	Low
• Integrate a qualitative and responsible quantitative approach into research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise diversity of roles, activities, and outputs of researchers in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12

• Recognise research manager and research management activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise research technician and technical support activities in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise research integrity and inclusivity and gender equality in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognise Open Science practices and societal impact of research in research assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Inform research assessors on the added value of reformed research assessment criteria	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Monitor any reforms in research assessment criteria for negative and unwanted effects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(34) How would you prioritise the following actions on assessment initiatives?

	Top	High	Low
• Sign the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and Join CoARA as a member	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Identify structural and administrative barriers to reform research assessment systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Collect and share best practices on reforming existing research assessment systems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(35) How would you prioritise the following actions on career support?

	Top	High	Low
• Review and improve the career support and professional development of researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Provide professional mentoring to researchers by experts in and outside organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(36) How would you prioritise the following actions on TTLMs?

	Top	High	Low
• Review regulations and status of TTLMs in national context and locally at organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Define TTLMs in discussion and close collaboration with researchers at organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Develop an action plan for future implementation of defined TTLMs at organisations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders on TTLMs to collect and share best practices on TTLMs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13

• Engage with national research funders on the need for long-term funding for TTLMs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
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(37) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 5?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 6

Pillar 6 focuses on Balanced Circulation of Talents and Making the Union an Attractive Destination.

This includes actions on making the European Union attractive to researchers.

The balanced circulation of researchers refers to the movement of researchers equally to and from countries in Europe.

(38) How would you prioritise the following actions on a competitive European Union?

	Top	High	Low
• Review and internally discuss support to attract and reintegrate returning researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Review and internally discuss support to facilitate dual positions in different countries	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engage with key stakeholders to contribute to the balanced circulation of researchers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(39) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 6?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 7

Pillar 7 focuses on Support Actions for Research Careers.

This includes actions on talent platforms, European Charter for Researchers, and Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R).

[EURAXESS](#) is a European network and platform to foster the mobility and career development of researchers.

The [ERA Talent Platform](#) is an online gateway offering a range of services to support researchers and organisations.

14

The [European Charter for Researchers](#) is a set of principles defining the relationship between researchers and employers/funders.

The [HRS4R](#) is a defined process to implement the European Charter for Researchers at organisations and is linked to an award.

(40) How would you prioritise the following actions on talent platforms?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the EURAXESS portal and ERA Talent Platform among researchers	●	●	●
• Disseminate job/grant opportunities in the EURAXESS portal and ERA Talent Platform	●	●	●

(41) How would you prioritise the following actions on the European Charter for Researchers?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the European Charter for Researchers among researchers	●	●	●
• Endorse and implement the European Charter for Researchers at organisations	●	●	●

(42) How would you prioritise the following actions on the HRS4R award?

	Top	High	Low
• Raise awareness on the HRS4R award and its relevance for researchers	●	●	●
• Apply formally to the European Commission to receive the HRS4R award	●	●	●

(43) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 7?

1000 character(s) maximum

Pillar 8

Pillar 8 focuses on the Monitoring of Research Careers.

This includes actions on the new Research and Innovation Careers Observatory (ReICO).

[ReICO](#) is a new tool being developed which aims to be the main source for reliable data and information on research careers.

ReICO is a joint initiative by the European Commission and Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD).

(44) How would you prioritise the following actions on ReICO?

15

	Top	High	Low
• Engage with OECD and key stakeholders on development and implementation of ReICO	●	●	●
• Review and internally discuss collection and provision of relevant internal data for ReICO	●	●	●

(45) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above actions in Pillar 8?

1000 character(s) maximum

TTLMs

The SECURE project has developed 9 principles to define tenure track-like models (TTLMs):

(1) **Stability:** Researchers expect to have a clear and defined progression pathway that leads to permanent employment or an open-ended contract.

(2) **Transparency:** Researchers expect to have been thoroughly informed about the recruitment process, expected skills and competencies, selection criteria, working conditions and benefits, contractual status, and progression pathway(s).

(3) **Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment:** Researchers expect a competitive recruitment process with selection criteria that consider a diverse range of skills, competencies, and experiences (including intersectoral) in an inclusive and accessible manner.

(4) **Fair Pay and Benefits:** Researchers expect to receive attractive and commensurate remuneration and benefits with pay increases linked to progression, and to be made aware of the review of remuneration conditions, for example once they are successful in obtaining a permanent or open-ended contract. This should include access to adequate social protection.

(5) **Recognition through Career Pathways:** Researchers expect to be supported to pursue their career ambitions, with recognition for diverse contributions and outputs (e.g. across research, teaching, leadership, innovation, and engagement) through a range of possible career pathways. Where possible this should include the opportunity for non-linear, multi-career, and hybrid paths that are recognised on par with linear career paths.

(6) **Professional Development:** Researchers expect to have the time and ability to engage in meaningful professional and career development, including access to relevant training and opportunities (including in other sectors) that develop the leadership qualities necessary for academic progression and independence. Mentoring schemes should also be offered.

(7) **Inclusive and Healthy Working Environments:** Researchers expect to work in environments that welcome and value diversity, which are healthy and accessible, and have no tolerance for bullying, harassment, or pressure to compromise research integrity.

16

(8) **Supportive Management:** Researchers expect to have a named line manager (or named senior member of staff) with allocated time, availability, and expertise to offer them regular points to check in, appraise their performance, and provide the support needed to achieve their full potential.

(9) **Responsible Evaluation:** Researchers expect there to be a formal evaluation process at set checkpoints and against clear criteria. These criteria and timeline should be made available to them before or at the time of appointment. Where it becomes clear that they may not meet the criteria, researchers expect this to be communicated as early as possible and a support plan and process of remediation should be put in place.

(46) How would you prioritise the following principles for TTLMs?

	Top	High	Low
• Stability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Transparency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Competitive and Inclusive Recruitment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Fair Pay and Benefits	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Recognition through Career Pathways	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Professional Development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Inclusive and Healthy Working Environments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Supportive Management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Responsible Evaluation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(47) Do you see any gaps or have any comments on the above principles for TTLMs?

1000 character(s) maximum

(48) What do you think are the main reasons for the precarity of research careers?

1000 character(s) maximum

• (49) Do you think TTLMs are the ideal way to reduce the precarity of research careers?

- Yes
 No

• Please explain

1000 character(s) maximum

17

(50) Do you have any final comments on the actions of the Research Career Framework or principles for TTLMs?

1000 character(s) maximum

Thank You!

Thank you for taking the time to respond to this survey and help the SECURE project to improve research careers in Europe!

• Would you like to be kept informed of the results of the survey and the SECURE project?

- Yes
 No

• Please enter your email address

100 character(s) maximum

18

SECURE PROJECT

IF YOU WOULD LIKE TO KNOW MORE ABOUT OUR PROJECT ACTIVITIES

E-MAIL US info@secureproject

